

Rice leaf miner *Hydrellia griseola* in Australia

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The smaller rice leaf miner *H. griseola* (Fallén) (Diptera: Ephydriidae) damaged 30% of the rice crop in the Mareeba Irrigation Area (17° 05' S, 145° 20' E) in Sep 1987. It was found in the Philippines in 1979-80; it had previously been found in Europe, North and South America, temperate regions of Asia, and Malaysia. This is the first record of this species in Australia.

Damage occurred after fields were irrigated in Sep 1987. Larva-mined leaf damage appeared as bare patches at the edges of bays and in deeper water (100-150 mm) (see figure). Heavy infestations caused general thinning of plant stands.

Aerial application of trichlorophon at 700 ml of 625 g/liter per hectare gave excellent control.

General thinning of plant stand and damage at edge of bay. North Queensland, Australia, 1987.

Insecticide was applied by a Piper Pawnee agricultural aircraft fitted with eight A U 5,000 micronaire units producing droplets of 150 microns.

Two braconid parasites were reared from field-collected *H. griseola*:

Dolichogenidea sp. (Microgasterinae) and an unidentified species of Alysinae, but the level of parasitization found would not make an impact on the pest population. □

Yield loss caused by rice stem borers (SB) in southern Bhutan

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We sampled fields heavily infested with SB *Chilo* sp. and *Scirpophaga* sp.

Varieties planted were Jaya, BR153, and Dhursray at Bhur Experimental Farm and a traditional variety in a farmer's field. Ten hills with different number of whiteheads were sampled from each field.

No significant differences in yield were observed in Jaya and Dhursray; for the traditional variety, a slight yield increase was found in plants attacked by one whitehead (see table). Only in BR153 did hills with more than 2 whiteheads have significantly lower yields. This implies that hills with as many as four whiteheads may compensate for insect damage. □

Rice SB damage (whiteheads) and yield of 4 rice varieties.^a Gayleghug, Bhutan, Nov 1988.

Whiteheads (no./hill)	Tillers (no./hill)	SB (no./hill)	Panicles (no./hill)	Yield (g/hill)
<i>Jaya</i>				
0	10.0 b	0.1 d	10.7 b	19.1 a
1	9.9 b	3.4 c	10.3 b	19.4 a
2	12.2 ab	6.0 ab	11.4 ab	15.3 a
3	11.2 b	7.0 a	9.5 b	13.2 a
4	14.6 a	4.3 bc	13.5 a	16.9 a
<i>BR 153</i>				
0	13.4 a	0.2 b	21.2 a	20.5 a
1	11.7 a	4.3 a	11.5 a	16.3 ab
2	13.7 a	5.6 a	12.8 a	16.0 ab
3	12.6 a	2.9 a	11.0 a	13.4 b
4	13.2 a	4.9 a	11.7 a	10.2 b
<i>Traditional (farmer's field)</i>				
0	8.9 a	5.6 a	8.7 a	14.0 ab
1	11.4 a	7.1 a	10.9 a	15.7 a
2	9.8 a	8.2 a	9.7 a	10.0 b
3	9.5 a	6.1 a	9.0 a	9.7 b
4	11.6 a	5.0 a	10.6 a	9.5 b
<i>Traditional (Dhursray)</i>				
0	8.9 a	2.5 a	9.0 a	17.8 a
1	10.0 a	4.3 a	9.9 a	21.3 a
2	9.0 a	4.5 a	8.1 a	11.5 a
3	11.0 a	4.4 a	10.5 a	10.3 a

^a In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different from each other at the 5% level by DMRT.